

Viscosity Behaviour of Natural Humic Acids Isolated from Diverse Soil Types

Chhabi Datta and S. K. Mukherjee*

The viscosity behaviour of humic acids isolated from five different soils have been studied which reveal their polyelectrolytic nature. The values of intrinsic viscosities of four samples are in the range of 10.63 to 17.86 ml/gm. and that of one sample equal to 27.78 ml/gm. The viscosity average molecular weights of the respective humic acids range from 2.7×10^4 to 1.46×10^5 .

A large number of attempts have been made in recent years by several investigators¹⁻³ to show viscometrically the polyelectrolyte behaviour of coal humic acids. Piret *et al.*⁴ have demonstrated the non-spherical polyelectrolyte behaviour and polydispersity of humic acids, whereas Flaig and Beutelspacher⁵ have shown that both natural and synthetic humic acids are spherical in shape.

It has been pointed out that humic acid is a polyelectrolyte. The most interesting property which distinguishes a polyelectrolyte from a neutral polymer is the way in which the reduced viscosity ($\eta_{sp/c}$) is dependent on concentration. The reduced viscosity of a neutral macromolecular solution generally decreases with decreasing concentration, while for a salt-free polyelectrolyte, the curve shows a sharp increase in the reduced viscosity at lower concentration. The sharp increase has been attributed by Fuoss⁶ as due partially to molecular dilation of the polyelectrolyte caused by the repulsion of similarly charged, ionisable groups which dissociate upon dilution. Therefore, in the case of a polyelectrolyte the intrinsic viscosity, which serves as a measure of the molecular weight, cannot be correctly evaluated unless the measurements are done in presence of salts, which suppress the electrical charge.

The ordinary viscosity plot clearly does not permit in this case a meaningful extrapolation of $\eta_{sp/c}$ to zero concentration. Fuoss and Strauss⁶ found that the curve of reduced viscosity versus concentration could be described by an equation of the form

$$\frac{sp}{C} = \frac{A}{1+B\sqrt{C}} \quad \dots (1)$$

* Vice-Chancellor, University of Kalyani, W. Bengal.

1. P. N. Mukherjee and A. Lahiri. *Fuel*, 1958, **37**, 220-228.
2. P. N. Mukherjee and A. Lahiri. *J. Colloid Sci.*, 1956, **11**, 240.
3. N. Rajalakshmi, S. R. Sivarajan and R. D. Vold. *J. Colloid Sci.*, 1959, **14**, 419-429.
4. E. L. Piret, R. G. White, H. C. Walther Jr. and A. J. Madden. Jr. *Sci. Proc. Royal Dublin Soc.*, 1960, **1**, Series A, 69-79.
5. W. Flaig and H. Beutelspacher. *Landbouwkundig Tijdschrift*, 1954, **68**, 306.
6. R. M. Fuoss and U. P. Strauss. *J. Polymer Sci.*, 1948, **3**, 246, 602.

A is clearly the limiting value of η_{sp}/c , i.e., $A = [\eta]$. Now a plot of reciprocal of reduced viscosity versus the square root of concentration gives a straight line which apparently allows the intrinsic viscosity of a salt-free polyelectrolyte to be determined by extrapolation.

For macromolecules, the relationship between the intrinsic viscosity and the molecular weight is represented⁷ as

$$[\eta] = K M^{-\alpha} \quad \dots (2)$$

where both K and α are constants, their values depending on the nature of the solute and solvent and on the temperature. For flexible linear polymers α varies between 0.50 and 0.80 and for rod shaped molecules α is equal to 1.8. Hence, the viscosity average molecular weight, M_v , can be calculated from the above equation if K and α are known or at least some plausible values of them are assumed.

EXPERIMENTAL

Five different types of soil, listed in Table I, have been selected for the isolation of humic acids used in the present investigation. The organic matter contents of these soils vary from 0.26—5.50%. Humic acid was isolated and purified by the usual procedure^{8,9}.

Sodium humate was prepared by treating a concentrated suspension of electro dialysed humic acid with a dilute solution of NaOH to pH between 8 and 9. The solution was then concentrated and the sodium salt was precipitated by the addition of alcohol-acetone mixture. The precipitate was then centrifuged and freed from any excess of alkali after washing several times with 95% neutral alcohol. The salt was finally dried at 85° and preserved in a desiccator.

The viscosity measurements were done in the Cannon-Fenske capillary viscometer having a flow time for 5.0 ml of water (distilled) of 226.80 sec.

All these measurements were done in a water thermostat maintained at $35 \pm 0.1^\circ$ by a toluene vapour thermoregulator operating in conjunction with an electronic relay system.

The solutions being very diluted their densities were assumed to be identical with that of pure water. The intrinsic viscosities were calculated as usual by graphical extrapolation.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The results of viscosity measurements are shown in Figs. 1 and 2. The graphs are typical of polyelectrolytes. Thus, addition of salt (0.1 M NaCl) suppresses polyelectrolytic character and lowers the reduced viscosity (Figs. 1 and 2 shown as typical curves)*. The reduced viscosity of sodium humate solution from Palampur soil in 0.1 M NaCl shows a maximum at about 0.08 gm/100 ml. The values of intrinsic viscosities of different humic acids obtained by extrapolation of the viscosity curve in presence of 0.1 M NaCl are given

7. C. Tanford—Physical Chemistry of Macromolecules, John Wiley and Sons, Inc., 1965.

8. Chhabi Datta and S. K. Mukherjee. *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1968, **45**, 555.

9. Chhabi Datta. D. Phil Thesis, 1968, University of Calcutta.

* In order to save space the other graphs are not included.

in Table I. They lie in the region of 4.25-5.8 ml/gm., whereas for synthetic humic acids the values range from 4.2-10.0 ml/gm at 35°¹⁰.

FIG. 1. Na-HUMATE FROM PALAMPUR

FIG. 2. Na-HUMATE FROM DARJEELING

10. S. Sur and S. K. Mukherjee. *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1969, 46, 459.

The values of intrinsic viscosities obtained by extrapolation according to Fuoss and Strauss equation (1) to zero concentration of the salt-free sodium humate from different soils are in the range 10.63 to 17.86 ml/gm excepting that from Darjeeling soil which has got a much higher value (27.78 ml/gm). So, the intrinsic viscosities of different humic acids (except that from Darjeeling) are small compared with that of synthetic polyelectrolytes (18.0–60.0 ml/gm)¹⁰. It is known that the presence of branched structures along the main polymer chain decreases the intrinsic viscosity of the polymer. The low intrinsic viscosities of different humic acids therefore, suggest branching. Darjeeling humic acid has got a larger value of intrinsic viscosity which may be due to either of all such characters as long chain, high flexibility and high molecular weight.

The effect of rate of shear, if any, on viscosity, has not been studied. However, for molecules of relatively low intrinsic viscosity the rate of shear has generally no appreciable effect on $[\eta]$ ⁷. In order to calculate the viscosity average molecular weight from equation (2), firstly, the parameter K has been evaluated putting $\alpha = 0.5$ and 0.8 in the above equation and using the values of the intrinsic viscosity and molecular weight of Piret's peat humic acid⁴. Using these values of K corresponding to $\alpha = 0.5$ and 0.8 the viscosity average molecular weights of different humic acids have been estimated and shown in Table I.

TABLE I

Humic Acid	Organic Matter content of the soil %	$[\eta]$ Salt free (from Fuoss Strauss plot) ml/gm.	$[\eta]$ 0.1 M NaCl ml/gm.	Viscosity Average Molecular Weight $\times 10^{-4}$
Palampur	2.60	12.50	5.80	2.77— 2.95
Chinsura	0.67	10.63	4.25	2.14— 2.27
Dehra Dun	5.50	16.81	5.10	4.02— 5.34
Darjeeling	2.90	27.78	4.80	7.53—14.60
Jodhpur	0.26	17.86	5.10	4.33— 6.03

The molecular weights range from 2.14×10^4 to 14.60×10^4 , and are of the order of those observed in the case of synthetic humic acids⁴.

Thanks are due to Prof. B. N. Ghosh, for allowing laboratory facilities and to the U.G.C. for financial assistance to one of us (C.D.).

Colloid Research Laboratory,
Department of Pure Chemistry,
University College of Science,
Calcutta-9.

Received May 15, 1970